

AI as a Privilege of Teachers?

Asymmetric Usage Patterns and Barriers to Student Access in K-12 Education: Evidence from Germany in International Comparison

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Abstract

This study examines the paradox of asymmetric artificial intelligence (AI) use in K-12 education, where teachers embrace AI tools for personal and professional purposes while restricting student access. Drawing on data from the LENS-AI study (N=381) conducted in Baden-Württemberg, Germany, and situating these findings within the broader international research landscape, we identify a consistent pattern across educational systems: teachers act as gatekeepers who benefit from generative AI while protecting students from its use. Our mixed-methods survey reveals that 77% of German teachers use AI privately, yet only 64% employ it for instruction, and 57% completely prohibit student use for ideation tasks. Correlation analyses reveal that both private and educational AI use correlate positively with perceived life improvement and enjoyment, with educational use showing notably stronger associations ($\rho=.49$ and $\rho=.57$, respectively) than private use ($\rho=.30$ and $\rho=.33$). Teachers using AI in instruction also report greater trust in AI tools ($\rho=.44$) and less fear ($\rho=-.21$), suggesting that hands-on professional experience may be particularly effective in fostering positive attitudes. These findings align with international studies from the United States, Australia, China, and Europe, and partially support technology acceptance models, as experience correlates with positive attitudes. However, the persistent gap between teacher and student AI use—despite positive teacher attitudes—suggests that professional identity concerns and risk perceptions focused on cognitive threats (89% of stated concerns) operate as additional barriers beyond TAM constructs. We propose an integrated framework for understanding teacher AI adoption that synthesizes international findings and offers three policy recommendations: professional development addressing values and role perceptions, school development providing legal certainty and spaces for collegial experimentation, and education policy acknowledging cultural and professional dimensions of AI integration.

Keywords: artificial intelligence in education, teacher attitudes, technology adoption, K-12 education, generative AI, international comparison

1 Introduction

The rapid proliferation of generative artificial intelligence (AI) systems, particularly large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, has altered the landscape of educational technology discourse since late 2022. Unlike previous technological innovations in education, generative AI presents a qualitatively different challenge: these systems bare the potential to function not as passive tools but as interactive partners capable of co-constructing knowledge, generating content, and providing personalized feedback at scale. This potential to transform education has profound implications

for teaching and learning, raising questions about the nature of human cognition, creativity, and the fundamental purposes of education.

The international discourse on AI in education has predominantly focused on competency frameworks, particularly AI literacy, data literacy, and prompt engineering skills . However, systematic empirical evidence regarding how AI systems are actually integrated into educational processes, especially by students under teacher guidance, remains remarkably scarce. This gap is particularly significant given the transformative potential attributed to generative and agentic AI systems .

This article addresses this gap by presenting findings from the LENS-AI study, a comprehensive mixed-methods investigation of teacher attitudes and AI usage patterns in Baden-Württemberg, Germany. Crucially, we situate these findings within the growing body of international research on teacher AI adoption, drawing comparisons with studies from the United States , Australia , China , Hong Kong , and various European contexts .

This international comparative approach serves multiple purposes. First, it allows us to identify whether patterns observed in Germany represent local phenomena or reflect broader cross-cultural dynamics in teacher AI adoption. Second, it enables the development of more robust theoretical frameworks by testing explanatory models across diverse educational systems. Third, it provides a foundation for evidence-based policy recommendations that account for both universal patterns and context-specific factors.

Our central research questions are:

1. What are the patterns of private and professional AI use among German teachers, and how do these compare with international findings?
2. How do teachers regulate student access to AI tools, and what concerns drive these decisions?
3. What factors predict teacher AI adoption, and to what extent do established technology acceptance models explain observed patterns?
4. What implications do these findings have for teacher professional development and education policy?

The article proceeds as follows: Section 2 reviews the international literature on teacher AI adoption, identifying key themes and gaps. Section 3 presents our theoretical framework, synthesizing established technology acceptance models with emerging perspectives on AI as a distinctive technological category. Section 4 describes our methodology. Section 5 presents results from the LENS-AI study. Section 6 provides an international comparison of key findings. Section 7 discusses implications, and Section 8 offers conclusions and recommendations.

2 Literature Review: International Perspectives on Teacher AI Adoption

2.1 International Examples of Teacher AI Use

Research on teacher adoption of generative AI has expanded rapidly since 2023, with studies emerging from diverse educational contexts worldwide. A consistent finding across this literature is the discrepancy between teacher awareness of AI tools and their actual integration into classroom practice. Riegel et al. (2025), in a mixed-methods study of approximately 195 teachers and 61 administrators across five US states, found that while teachers generally possessed knowledge about

AI, fewer than half actually used AI tools in their professional practice. This awareness-adoption gap suggests that barriers to AI integration extend beyond mere familiarity with the technology.

Similarly, Cheah et al. (2025), surveying 89 teachers in predominantly rural Idaho, reported that fewer than 50% of respondents felt prepared for generative AI integration. Notably, when teachers did use AI, it was primarily for activities outside direct instruction, including lesson preparation, task formatting, and administrative duties, rather than for real-time learning activities with students. This pattern of backstage versus frontstage AI use emerges consistently across international studies and represents a key finding that our German data both confirms and extends.

The Australian context provides additional perspective. Collie and Martin (2024), in a large-scale survey of 339 K-12 teachers, examined motivational and contextual factors influencing AI adoption. Their findings highlighted the importance of leadership style, with autonomy-supportive leadership significantly predicting teachers' valuing of generative AI. This valuing, in turn, correlated strongly with actual integration of AI into teaching tasks and learning activities. The study underscores that teacher AI adoption cannot be understood in isolation from the broader organizational and cultural context of schools.

2.2 Teacher Attitudes and Perceptions

International research consistently documents ambivalent teacher attitudes toward AI in education. Teachers recognize potential benefits while simultaneously expressing significant concerns. Mujahidah et al. (2025), surveying 205 teachers in Indonesian suburban schools, found predominantly positive attitudes, with teachers expecting AI to personalize instruction, address individual learning needs, enhance teaching quality, and reduce administrative burdens. Teachers also expressed enthusiasm for AI as a tool for fostering creativity and problem-solving.

However, this optimism is tempered by substantial concerns. Bateman (2024), in an exploratory case study involving 225 US K-12 teachers and focus groups with 12 educators, documented a dual perception of ChatGPT. Teachers valued the time savings, resource accessibility, and support for lesson preparation that ChatGPT offered. Simultaneously, they expressed serious concerns about academic integrity, particularly the potential for student cheating. Importantly, Bateman found that familiarity with ChatGPT correlated with more positive attitudes: teachers who were more comfortable with the tool perceived greater pedagogical benefits and fewer risks.

Kladaki et al. (2024), studying 67 arts and performing arts teachers in Greece, identified a similarly ambivalent stance. Teachers anticipated benefits including enhanced student motivation, creativity, critical thinking support, and improved differentiation for students with special needs. Yet they also feared student plagiarism, misinformation, and potential negative impacts on creativity. This ambivalence—the simultaneous recognition of promise and peril—characterizes teacher attitudes across national contexts.

2.3 Factors Influencing Teacher AI Adoption

Research has identified multiple factors that predict teacher AI adoption, extending beyond simple technology acceptance constructs. Wang et al. (2025), studying 230 mathematics teachers in China using an integrated Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) framework, found that attitudes toward AI, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control all directly influenced actual AI use. Critically, their study highlighted the role of AI awareness: familiarity with generative AI enhanced perceptions of usefulness and ease of use, which in turn fostered positive attitudes and increased adoption.

Galindo-Domínguez et al. (2024), in a survey of 445 Spanish teachers across primary, secondary,

and higher education, demonstrated a significant correlation between digital competence and positive AI attitudes. Teachers with higher digital skills showed greater readiness and more favorable dispositions toward AI use, regardless of gender, age, or subject area. This finding suggests that building digital competence may be a pathway to increasing AI acceptance.

Beege et al. (2024), studying 102 STEM teachers in German secondary schools, provided nuanced insights into the relationship between perceived benefits, risks, and AI adoption. Using a path-analytic model with manifest variables, they showed that AI-related competencies and perceived benefits, partly mediated by perceived effects on teaching quality, positively predicted current use and especially future use intentions. Notably, perceived risks did not significantly inhibit adoption, indicating that German STEM teachers were willing to engage with AI despite acknowledged downsides. The inverse relationship between perceived benefits and risks points to an affect heuristic in teacher decision-making, whereby positive evaluations outweigh abstract risk considerations.

2.4 Pre-Service Teachers and Professional Preparation

Several studies have examined AI attitudes among pre-service teachers, providing insights into the preparation of future educators. Moorhouse (2024), conducting qualitative interviews with 27 beginning English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers in Hong Kong, identified a significant preparation gap. First-year teachers who had experience with ChatGPT during their training showed readiness to use AI and recognized its potential. In contrast, beginning teachers without such experience felt underprepared and demonstrated limited AI knowledge. This finding underscores the importance of integrating AI education into initial teacher preparation programs.

Musood and Kaur (2025), surveying 428 pre-service teachers in India, explored the relationships among digital competence, mindful attention awareness, and AI attitudes. The study found that both higher digital competence and greater mindfulness predicted more positive AI attitudes, with these factors explaining over 79% of the variance in attitudes. Mindfulness mediated a substantial portion of the effect of digital competence, suggesting that reflective engagement with technology may be as important as technical skills.

Hu et al. (2025), using metaphor analysis with 265 Chinese pre-service teachers, revealed predominantly positive conceptualizations of AI in education. Participants characterized AI using metaphors of guidance, growth, resources, and discovery, though some also perceived AI as challenging or dual-natured. Sentiment analysis indicated approximately 62% positive orientations, with variations based on prior AI education experience.

2.5 Gaps in the Literature

Despite the growing body of research, several gaps remain. First, most studies focus on teacher attitudes and adoption without systematically examining how teachers regulate student access to AI. The teacher-as-gatekeeper dynamic, while implicit in many findings, has not been theorized or empirically investigated in depth. Second, cross-national comparative analyses remain rare, limiting our understanding of universal versus context-specific patterns. Third, few studies examine the relationship between private AI use and professional practice, missing an opportunity to understand how personal experience shapes professional adoption. The present study addresses these gaps through a comprehensive investigation of German teachers that systematically compares findings with international research.

3 Theoretical Framework

3.1 Technology Acceptance Models and Their Limitations

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM; Davis 1989) has dominated research on teacher technology adoption for decades. Meta-analyses confirm TAM as the most frequently used framework for explaining teacher technology use . The model posits that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use shape behavioral intentions, which in turn predict actual technology use. Extensions such as TAM2 and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) incorporate additional factors including subjective norms, facilitating conditions, and social influence .

The Will-Skill-Tool Model (WSTM; Knezek and Christensen 2016) offers an alternative perspective, emphasizing that successful technology integration requires motivation (Will), competence (Skill), and access (Tool). This model has been influential in educational technology policy, implicitly informing digitalization strategies that combine infrastructure investment, professional development, and motivational initiatives.

Both frameworks share an instrumental logic in which technology is conceptualized as a neutral tool whose adoption depends on individual attitudes and competencies. This assumption has proven heuristically valuable for understanding the adoption of earlier educational technologies such as interactive whiteboards or tablets. However, generative AI systems challenge this instrumental logic in fundamental ways.

3.2 Generative AI as a Distinctive Technological Category

Generative AI systems differ qualitatively from previous educational technologies. Rather than serving as passive tools that teachers manipulate, these systems function as interactive partners capable of co-constructing knowledge and generating novel outputs . This partnership follows a complementary rather than substitutive logic . Instead of replacing human capabilities, AI systems extend human agency by providing qualitatively different resources, including the ability to synthesize knowledge, generate diverse perspectives, and offer personalized feedback at scale.

In educational contexts, this means that AI systems are not passive instruments but active participants in teaching and learning processes. Their specific capabilities, such as natural language interaction, knowledge synthesis, and creative generation, enable new pedagogical possibilities while simultaneously raising novel challenges. The relational dynamics between teachers, students, and AI systems cannot be adequately captured by the unidirectional utility calculations of traditional acceptance models.

Furthermore, the WSTM loses predictive power when applied to generative AI. Natural language interfaces substantially reduce traditional skill barriers, enabling quasi-intuitive interaction without specialized technical training. The persistence of heterogeneous adoption patterns despite these reduced skill requirements, as documented across international studies and in our German data, suggests that factors beyond the three model dimensions are at play.

3.3 Context-Dependent Adoption and Professional Identity

International research points to the importance of contextual factors in shaping AI adoption. The consistent finding that teachers use AI more extensively for personal and preparatory purposes than for direct classroom instruction suggests that adoption decisions are highly context-dependent. Private technology use occurs in self-controlled, stable settings with few stakeholders, whereas institutional use involves complex networks of students, colleagues, administrators, parents, regulations, and organizational structures.

This context dependency intersects with questions of professional identity. Teaching has traditionally been understood as a fundamentally human activity involving relationship-building, moral guidance, and the cultivation of independent thinking . The introduction of AI systems that can perform some traditionally human functions, such as providing feedback, explaining concepts, or generating creative content, may threaten established role conceptions. Teachers may perceive AI not as an extension of their capabilities but as a challenge to their professional identity and autonomy.

Risk perceptions in the educational context appear to be filtered through professional identity concerns. As our data and international studies demonstrate, teacher concerns about AI overwhelmingly focus on cognitive risks to students, including loss of critical thinking, reduced independence, and diminished creativity, rather than on technical or practical risks. This focus on cognitive threats may reflect deeper anxieties about the changing nature of education and the teacher’s role within it.

3.4 An Integrated Framework for Teacher AI Adoption

Synthesizing international findings, we propose an integrated framework for understanding teacher AI adoption that incorporates four key dimensions:

1. **Technology Acceptance Factors:** Consistent with TAM and UTAUT, perceived usefulness, ease of use, and facilitating conditions influence adoption intentions. However, these factors operate differently across contexts.
2. **Context-Dependency:** Adoption decisions are shaped by the specific context of use. Private contexts with low stakes and high autonomy facilitate positive experiences, while institutional contexts with multiple stakeholders and accountability pressures activate different evaluative criteria.
3. **Professional Identity:** Teacher AI adoption is mediated by professional identity concerns, including perceptions of the teacher’s role, beliefs about human versus machine capabilities, and anxieties about role changes.
4. **Gatekeeping Dynamics:** Teachers occupy a gatekeeping position that allows them to regulate student access to AI. This gatekeeping function is shaped by risk perceptions, professional responsibilities, and institutional expectations.

This framework guides our analysis of the LENS-AI data and structures our international comparisons.

4 Methods

4.1 Study Design

The LENS-AI study (Leadership, Attitudes, Usage Types, and School Transformation Processes in the Context of Artificial Intelligence) employed a mixed-methods design combining standardized online surveying with qualitative analysis of open-ended responses . The study aimed to investigate:

- Teacher attitudes toward their own AI use and toward student AI use
- Actual domains of AI application (preparation, assessment, administration, individualization, creative projects)

- Perceived opportunities and risks of AI in school contexts

4.2 Participants and Sampling

Data collection occurred between June and September 2025. Participants were recruited primarily through publicly accessible email addresses of all schools in Baden-Württemberg, Germany. The study invitation was distributed through these channels, with participation being voluntary and anonymous. Additional recruitment occurred through direct outreach to schools.

A total of $N=381$ individuals began the questionnaire, of whom $N=247$ completed it fully. The final sample for analysis comprised $N=381$ participants, with valid response counts varying between $n=216$ and $n=381$ depending on specific items. Participants provided informed consent after receiving information about the study’s purpose and procedures.

4.3 Instrument

The survey instrument was developed specifically for this study and comprised four dimensions:

1. **Demographic data and school context:** Age, gender, role, school type, and subjects taught
2. **Teacher AI usage practices:** Private and professional use, frequency, application domains
3. **Perceptions of student AI use:** Attitudes toward student use, observed usage patterns, regulatory approaches
4. **General attitudes toward AI in education:** Perceived benefits and risks, future expectations, professional development needs

The questionnaire combined closed-ended items (predominantly Likert scales) with open-ended response options, enabling both quantitative and qualitative analysis.

4.4 Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using R statistical software. Descriptive statistics characterized frequencies and distributions. Given the predominantly ordinal scaling and non-normal distributions of the data, Spearman correlations were calculated to examine relationships between variables .

It should be noted that due to the non-probability sampling design, the reported correlations are not generalizable to all teachers in Baden-Württemberg. However, they provide consistent indications of systematic relationships between usage contexts and attitudes that have rarely been empirically documented in previous research. The value of these analyses lies less in precise effect size quantification than in identifying theoretically relevant patterns that can inform further model development regarding technology acceptance and teacher professionalization in the context of AI.

Qualitative data (open-ended responses) were analyzed using content analysis procedures . Theory-guided category formation (deductive approach) was supplemented by categories derived inductively from the material.

4.5 Strengths and Limitations

The LENS-AI study covers an entire German federal state, enabling broad empirical approximation of the status quo of school AI use in Germany. The mixed-methods design permits differentiated

insights, with quantitative analyses documenting frequencies and relationships while qualitative analyses reveal interpretation patterns and contextual logics. Particularly relevant is that the study extends beyond competency questions to examine attitudinal dimensions that have rarely been empirically investigated in prior discourse.

However, several methodological limitations must be acknowledged. First, selection bias may occur because technology-affine teachers or schools with stronger digital engagement may be more likely to participate. Second, non-response bias is possible because not all contacted schools and teachers responded; differences between participants and non-participants may distort results. Third, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences or conclusions about temporal development. Finally, context-boundedness must be considered: findings reflect specific conditions in Baden-Württemberg and may not transfer directly to other German states or international contexts.

5 Results

5.1 Sample Description

The sample (N=285) was predominantly composed of teachers (74%, n=216), with school administrators comprising 16% (n=47), student teachers 4% (n=13), and university students 5% (n=15). The mean age was 41.79 years (SD=10.80, Median=42, range 20-65 years).

Figure 1: Distribution of professional roles among respondents (n = 224). Teachers comprised the majority (89.3%), followed by trainee teachers (5.4%), student teachers (4.0%), and others (1.3%).

School type distribution included primary schools (28%, n=63), special education centers (SBBZ) (33%, n=73), intermediate schools (Realschule) (15%, n=34), academic secondary schools (Gymna-

sium) (12%, n=34), comprehensive schools (Gemeinschaftsschule) (6%, n=16), and lower secondary schools (Werkrealschule) (3%, n=9).

Figure 2: Distribution of school types (n = 260). Special needs schools (SBBZ) represented the largest group (33.5%), followed by primary schools (29.6%), intermediate schools (13.5%), grammar schools (12.3%), comprehensive schools (5.0%), extended secondary schools (3.1%), and other school types (3.1%).

5.2 Private and Professional AI Use

5.2.1 Private AI Use

The survey documented a notable discrepancy between private and professional AI use. While 77% of respondents (n=192) use AI tools privately, only 65% (n=166) employ them in or for instruction.

Private AI use varied by school type: comprehensive school teachers showed the highest rate (100%, n=16), followed by secondary modern schools (89%), primary schools (73%), academic secondary schools (75%), special education centers (74%), and lower secondary schools (63%).

Usage frequency among private users indicated that 45% (n=80) used AI tools once weekly and 42% (n=73) multiple times weekly. Only 14% (n=22) reported daily or more frequent use, suggesting that AI has not yet become fully routinized even among users.

5.2.2 Professional AI Use

For educational purposes, 63% (n=180) of teachers reported using AI tools in or for instruction.

Professional use rates also varied by school type: comprehensive schools (92%, n=15) and lower secondary schools (88%, n=7) showed highest rates, followed by academic secondary schools (75%,

Figure 3: Teaching subjects reported by respondents ($n = 260$, multiple responses possible). German (61.5%), Mathematics (54.6%), Natural Sciences (43.1%), Arts/Music (35.4%), Social Sciences (34.6%), Other subjects (31.9%), Physical Education (28.1%), and Foreign Languages (27.7%).

Figure 4: Private use of generative AI tools ($n = 250$). The majority (76.8%) reported using AI tools privately, while 23.2% reported no private use.

Figure 5: Private AI use by school type (n = 250). Comprehensive schools showed the highest adoption rate (100%), followed by intermediate schools (88.6%), grammar schools (75.0%), SBBZ (74.1%), primary schools (73%), other schools (71.4%), and extended secondary schools (62%).

Figure 6: Frequency of private generative AI use among users (n = 192). Once per week (44.8%), multiple times per week (41.7%), multiple times daily (7.3%), and once daily (6.2%).

Figure 7: Use of AI tools for teaching purposes (n = 260). The majority (63.8%) reported using AI for teaching, while 36.2% did not use AI in educational contexts.

n=26), special education centers (61%, n=58), secondary modern schools (63%, n=25), and primary schools (53%, n=51).

5.3 Barriers and Motivations

The most frequently cited reasons for infrequent or absent AI use were: “I see no necessity” (30%, n=72), “I don’t know suitable applications” (15%, n=37), and “I lack technical knowledge” (15%, n=34). Notably, 25% (n=56) indicated they already use AI frequently.

Teachers’ assessment of AI tool relevance for lesson preparation was moderate: 24% (n=61) rated AI as “not at all important,” while 36% (n=94) indicated “moderately important.” Only 13% (n=36) rated AI tools as “very important” or “extremely important” for their lesson preparation.

5.4 Application Domains

Usage patterns varied substantially by application domain. For idea generation for instructional materials, 24% (n=63) never used AI tools, while 53% (n=136) used them sometimes to very frequently. For creating worksheets, tests, or presentations, 38% (n=99) completely abstained from AI support.

The highest acceptance occurred for research and explanation of complex topics: 63% (n=166) used AI at least sometimes for this purpose, and only 20% (n=52) never did. Administrative tasks such as grading showed the lowest AI integration, with 65% (n=170) never using AI for these purposes.

5.5 Attitudes and Acceptance Patterns

Overall, 65% (n=151) of respondents expressed desire for AI support in their work, while only 17% (n=43) rejected this.

Figure 8: Educational AI use by school type (n = 260). Comprehensive schools: 92.3% yes; extended secondary: 87.5% yes; grammar schools: 75.0% yes; SBBZ: 60.9% yes; intermediate: 62.9% yes; other: 87.5% yes; primary: 53.2% yes.

Figure 9: Reasons for current AI usage frequency (n = 260, multiple responses). “See no necessity” (30.0%), “Already use AI frequently” (24.6%), “Lack technical knowledge” (15.4%), “Don’t know suitable applications” (15.4%), “Lack time” (11.9%), “Too expensive” (5.4%), “Lack trust” (5.4%), and “No interest” (1.9%).

Figure 10: Reasons for AI usage frequency by school type (n = 260). Cross-tabulation showing variation in barriers across school types.

Figure 11: Importance of AI tools for lesson preparation (n = 260). Moderately important (36.5%), slightly important (26.5%), not important (23.1%), very important (11.5%), and extremely important (2.3%).

Figure 12: Frequency of AI use for specific teaching tasks (n = 260). Research and explaining complex topics was most common (often/very often: 32.3%), followed by generating ideas for materials (23.1%), creating worksheets/tests (10.8%), and automating administrative tasks (8.8%).

Figure 13: Desire for AI support in professional work (n = 250). Rather yes (45.2%), definitely yes (19.6%), don't know (18.4%), rather not (13.6%), and definitely not (3.2%).

Quality assessment of AI outputs was ambivalent: 48% (n=114) found it difficult to evaluate AI tool quality, and only 2% (n=5) trusted AI suggestions in the instructional context without reservation.

Figure 14: Perceptions of AI for inclusive teaching (n = 260). Agreement (agree/strongly agree) was highest for “AI helps create accessible materials faster” (69.2%), followed by “AI helps adapt materials for heterogeneous groups” (48.5%) and “AI-supported differentiation facilitates individual support” (45.8%). Concerns included difficulty assessing pedagogical quality (46.5% agree/strongly agree) and lack of trust in AI for inclusive pedagogy (64.6% agree/strongly agree).

Perceived benefits focused on efficiency gains: 75% (n=193) viewed time savings as the greatest advantage, followed by process acceleration (61%, n=153) and facilitation of routine tasks (58%, n=147). Only 21% (n=57) perceived quality improvement of work outcomes as a benefit.

5.6 Attitude Changes Through Practical Experience

A central finding concerns attitude change through practical AI use: 64% (n=102) of users reported that their attitude toward AI had become more positive, while only 4% (n=7) reported worsening. 32% (n=44) noted no change in their attitudes.

Professional satisfaction remained largely stable with AI use: 65% (n=200) reported no change, while 32% (n=53) noted an increase and only 3% (n=10) a decrease in satisfaction.

5.7 Perceived Student AI Use

Student AI use in instruction was even more limited: 57% (n=136) of teachers reported that students never used AI for ideation, 50% (n=120) never for creative design, and 49% (n=118) never for research. Regular student AI use was practiced by only a small minority.

Figure 15: Perceived benefits of AI use (n = 260, multiple responses). Saves working time (75.4%), accelerates processes (60.4%), facilitates routine tasks (58.5%), creates space for more important tasks (50.4%), provides expert knowledge (30.4%), promotes creativity (29.2%), enables faster problem analysis (28.5%), reduces errors (25.0%), improves quality of work (20.8%), increases motivation (17.7%), increases performance (17.3%), saves costs (8.8%), and no benefits perceived (4.6%).

5.8 Teacher Attitudes Toward Student AI Use

Teacher attitudes toward student AI use were characterized by ambivalence: while 52% (n=127) agreed that AI use prepares students for future requirements, 44% (n=107) demanded strict regulation due to potential cheating. Only 22% (n=54) believed students learn better through AI use.

5.9 Professional Development Needs

The perceived need for professional development on AI was high: 80% (n=191) saw a rather large or large need. For inclusive pedagogy, 52% (n=124) saw a large need, for sustainability 42% (n=99), and for education for sustainable development 50% (n=119).

5.10 Assessment of Future Developments

Regarding future developments, 90% (n=217) of respondents did not expect AI to replace teachers in the long term, but 32% (n=78) believed AI would fundamentally change required competencies. 48% (n=116) saw great opportunities for improving educational quality through AI.

Attitude Change through AI Usage

Figure 16: Change in attitude toward AI through practical use (n = 165, among educational AI users). More positive (64.2%), unchanged (32.1%), and more negative (3.6%).

Job Satisfaction Change through AI Usage

Figure 17: Change in job satisfaction through AI use (n = 166, among educational AI users). Unchanged (65.1%), somewhat increased (29.5%), somewhat decreased (3.0%), and strongly increased (2.4%).

Figure 18: Frequency of student AI use observed by teachers (n = 260). For generating ideas: never (56.6%), rarely (19.7%), sometimes (15.3%), often (6.8%), very often (1.6%). For creative design: never (50.2%), rarely (25.3%), sometimes (16.1%), often (7.2%), very often (1.6%). For research/explaining topics: never (49.4%), rarely (16.5%), sometimes (18.5%), often (10.8%), very often (5.2%).

Figure 19: Teacher attitudes toward student AI use (varying n due to filter). “AI promotes independence/creativity” (n = 258): partly agree 45.0%, somewhat disagree 27.5%, strongly disagree 15.5%, somewhat agree 12.0%. “Students learn better with AI” (n = 254): partly agree 48.0%, somewhat agree 23.2%, somewhat disagree 18.5%, strongly disagree 10.2%. “AI prepares for future” (n = 232): somewhat agree 46.6%, partly agree 33.6%, somewhat disagree 12.5%, strongly disagree 7.3%. “Should be strictly regulated” (n = 207): partly agree 47.8%, somewhat agree 29.0%, somewhat disagree 17.4%, strongly disagree 5.8%.

Figure 20: Professional development needs for AI (n = 260). Rather high need (46.5%), high need (33.1%), rather low need (15.8%), and low need (4.6%).

Figure 21: Teacher beliefs about AI's role in education (varying n). "AI will replace teachers" (n = 260): strongly disagree 66.9%, somewhat disagree 23.8%, partly agree 6.2%, somewhat agree 3.1%. "AI changes required competencies" (n= 241): strongly disagree 16.2%, somewhat disagree 29.0%, partly agree 26.6%, somewhat agree 28.2%. "Teachers need intensive AI training" (n = 126): strongly disagree 0.8%, somewhat disagree 4.0%, partly agree 19.0%, somewhat agree 76.2%. "AI offers great opportunities for education quality" (n = 222): strongly disagree 5.4%, somewhat disagree 15.3%, partly agree 37.8%, somewhat agree 41.4%.

6 Qualitative Results: Usage Contexts and Risk Assessments

The following qualitative categories reflect the breadth and variety of AI applications, not their usage frequency. The categorization of open responses shows the spectrum of exploratively used application domains, while quantitative data document actual usage routines.

6.1 Private versus Educational AI Usage Patterns

Qualitative analysis of application domains reveals different usage logics between private and educational contexts. Private AI use concentrated on three main areas:

Text creation and formulation assistance: Emails and letters, greeting cards and invitation texts, poems and speeches, official correspondence, text correction and reformulation.

Research and information retrieval: General internet research (as a Google substitute), knowledge questions and general education, fact-checking and information verification.

Question answering: Everyday problem solving, answering children’s questions, explaining complex topics, seeking advice on various topics, obtaining a second opinion.

Additional significant private applications included education and learning (homework help for own children, personal continuing education), cooking and recipes, and home, garden, and DIY projects. These usage forms are characterized by high autonomy, low external evaluation risks, and immediate personal benefit.

Educational AI use by teachers showed notably different emphases:

Communication and correspondence: Parent letters, emails, general correspondence, press articles and reports, speeches.

Assessment and documentation: Report card texts, reports, assessment criteria, school reports.

Text editing and optimization: Formulation assistance, text summaries, simplified language, text correction, translations.

Instructional materials and preparation: Worksheets, lesson plans, curriculum distribution plans (ranked fourth).

The top three categories comprised approximately 60% of all mentions and predominantly concerned school-organizational rather than directly instruction-related tasks.

Notably, the spectrum of AI tool applications was considerably broader in the private domain than in the educational context.

6.2 Perceived Risks of Student AI Use

Teacher risk perception regarding student AI use concentrated heavily on cognitive threats:

Loss of critical thinking and unreflective adoption of AI-curated information: Unreflective or uncritical adoption of AI results, loss or lack of critical thinking and questioning, blind trust in AI results.

Loss of independence and autonomous thinking: Loss of independent and autonomous thinking, dependence on AI and reduced self-reliance.

Misinformation and disinformation: False information and fake news, lack of source verification and truth checking.

The eight central risk categories additionally included creativity loss (declining creative abilities, reduced self-development), cheating and fraud (homework and exam cheating), reduced effort orientation (“laziness,” convenience), loss of basic skills (language skills, problem-solving, research competence), and superficial learning (lack of deep understanding, insufficient anchoring).

The frequency distribution revealed a strong focus: cognitive risks comprised 89% of all mentions, practical risks 8%, and technical and societal risks only 3%. This emphasis on cognitive threats reveals strong concerns about AI-induced changes in learning culture and shows that teachers anticipate less technical than pedagogical challenges from AI.

6.3 Ambivalence Between Potential Recognition and Implementation Barriers

Qualitative findings document a fundamental ambivalence: while teachers recognize specific and quite differentiated potentials of AI for inclusion, language support, and individualization, risk assessment is dominated by concerns about cognitive regression (89% of risk mentions). This discrepancy between recognized possibilities and practiced reservations mirrors the quantitatively documented context-dependent usage and points to deep-seated barriers that extend beyond rational cost-benefit calculations.

7 Correlation Analyses

A central aim of the study was to test whether positive attitudes toward AI correlate with more frequent use, distinguishing between private and educational application. Accordingly, the first hypothesis (H1) proposed that teachers who use AI tools privately more frequently ascribe more positive effects to them. The second hypothesis (H2) assumed that educational use would also correlate positively with attitudes.

Table 1: Spearman correlations between frequency of private generative AI use (1 = once per week, 4 = multiple times daily) or educational use (0 = No, 1 = Yes) and teacher attitudes toward AI. Positive values indicate that more frequent private use or educational use is associated with higher agreement with the respective statement.

Statement	Private Use		Educational Use	
	ρ	p	ρ	p
AI makes my life easier	.30	<.001	.49	<.001
AI is fun for me	.33	<.001	.57	<.001
AI overwhelms me	-.26	<.001	-.32	<.001
I trust AI suggestions	.07	.32	.44	<.001
I am afraid of AI	-.08	.27	-.21	<.001

Results showed that private AI tool use correlated significantly positively with the statements “AI makes my life easier” ($\rho = .30$, $p < .001$) and “AI is fun for me” ($\rho = .33$, $p < .001$). For the statement “AI overwhelms me,” a negative correlation emerged ($\rho = -.26$, $p < .001$). No significant correlations were found between private use and trust in AI tools ($\rho = .07$, $p = .32$) or fear of AI ($\rho = -.08$, $p = .27$).

For educational use, a consistent positive pattern emerged. Significant positive correlations existed with “AI makes my life easier” ($\rho = .49$, $p < .001$), “AI is fun for me” ($\rho = .57$, $p < .001$), and “I trust AI tool suggestions in the instructional context” ($\rho = .44$, $p < .001$). A significant negative correlation was found with “AI overwhelms me” ($\rho = -.32$, $p < .001$) and “I am afraid of AI” ($\rho = -.21$, $p < .001$).

Thus, both Hypothesis 1 (H1) and Hypothesis 2 (H2) were clearly confirmed. Teachers who use AI more frequently, whether privately or in educational contexts, report more positive attitudes

toward AI. The correlation coefficients for educational use are notably stronger than for private use, suggesting that hands-on experience with AI in professional contexts may be particularly effective in fostering positive attitudes.

In a further analysis step, we tested whether frequency of private use (H3) correlates with more positive assessments of student use. We expected that frequent users would more strongly emphasize potentials for independence, better learning, future preparation, and differentiation.

Table 2: Spearman correlations between frequency of private generative AI use (1 = once per week, 4 = multiple times daily) and assessments of student AI use. Positive values indicate that more frequent private use is associated with higher agreement with the respective statement.

Statement	ρ	p
AI promotes student independence/creativity	.08	.28
Students learn better with AI	.10	.18
AI prepares students for the future	.06	.42
AI facilitates differentiation and individual support	.15	<.05
Student AI use should be strictly regulated	-.14	.05

Results showed a differentiated picture. A significant positive correlation was found only for the statement that AI facilitates differentiation and thus individual student support ($\rho = .15$, $p < .05$). For other dimensions, no systematic correlations with private usage frequency emerged. Thus, H3 was only partially supported.

7.1 Attitudes Toward Student Use

Beyond attitudes toward own use, teacher assessments of student AI use were also examined. We investigated whether own usage practice, private or educational, correlated with more positive or negative evaluations of student use.

Table 3: Spearman correlations between frequency of private generative AI use or educational use and teacher assessments of student AI use.

Statement	Private Use		Educational Use	
	ρ	p	ρ	p
AI promotes independence/creativity	.08	.28	.20	<.01
Students learn better with AI	.10	.18	.23	<.001
AI prepares for the future	.06	.42	.16	<.01
AI facilitates differentiation	.15	<.05	.40	<.001
Should be strictly regulated	-.14	.05	-.27	<.001

Results showed that private use correlated with student use assessments only selectively: a significant positive correlation was found for the statement that AI facilitates differentiation and individual support ($\rho = .15$, $p < .05$), and a marginally significant negative correlation for the view that student use should be strictly regulated ($\rho = -.14$, $p = .05$). For other dimensions such as independence, learning, or future preparation, no systematic correlations emerged.

For educational use, a clear and consistent pattern emerged: teachers who used AI in instruction agreed more strongly that AI promotes independence and creativity ($\rho = .20$, $p < .01$), that students

learn better with AI ($\rho = .23$, $p < .001$), that AI prepares students for the future ($\rho = .16$, $p < .01$), and that AI-supported differentiation facilitates individual support ($\rho = .40$, $p < .001$). Notably, educational users showed significantly less agreement with the statement that student AI use should be strictly regulated ($\rho = -.27$, $p < .001$).

Overall, findings suggest that both private and educational AI use are associated with more positive evaluations of student AI use. The associations are considerably stronger for educational use, indicating that direct professional experience with AI in teaching may be particularly influential in shaping teachers' views on student AI use. Teachers with educational AI experience not only recognize more opportunities (differentiation, independence, learning outcomes, future preparation) but also show less inclination toward strict regulation of student AI use. This suggests that hands-on professional experience helps teachers develop a more nuanced and balanced perspective on the integration of AI in educational contexts.

8 International Comparison

8.1 Adoption Patterns Across Countries

Comparing our German findings with international studies reveals striking consistencies. The gap between AI awareness or private use and actual classroom integration documented in our study (77% private use versus 64% professional use, with even lower rates of student use) mirrors patterns observed across diverse educational systems.

Riegel et al. (2025) reported that fewer than half of US teachers actually used AI tools despite general awareness. Cheah et al. (2025) found similar patterns in rural Idaho, where AI use occurred primarily outside direct instruction. Collie and Martin (2024) documented that even in Australia, where positive attitudes toward AI were associated with autonomy-supportive leadership, actual integration into learning activities remained variable.

Beege et al. (2024), studying German STEM teachers, reported low current AI use but high future expectations, a pattern consistent with our broader sample. Wang et al. (2025) found that among Chinese mathematics teachers, actual use was influenced by attitudes, norms, and perceived control, but the study also emphasized that awareness and familiarity were prerequisites for adoption.

Our findings extend this pattern: German teachers using AI in instruction show stronger positive attitude correlations than those using AI only privately, suggesting that professional application may be particularly influential in shaping positive perceptions.

8.2 The Gatekeeper Function

Our finding that teachers act as gatekeepers, using AI themselves while restricting student access, aligns with international evidence. The 57% of German teachers who completely prohibit student AI use for ideation reflects broader concerns documented across studies. Bateman (2024) noted US teacher concerns about student cheating as a primary barrier to allowing student use. Kladaki et al. (2024) found Greek arts teachers feared plagiarism, misinformation, and creativity reduction when students use AI.

This gatekeeping function appears to be a cross-cultural phenomenon rooted in professional responsibility concerns. Teachers perceive themselves as responsible for protecting students from potential cognitive harms while simultaneously deriving personal and professional benefits from AI tools. This asymmetry creates what might be termed a “privilege of the teacher”—a term that captures the differential access patterns we document.

8.3 Risk Perception Patterns

The concentration of German teacher concerns on cognitive risks (89% of mentions) resonates with international findings. Tripathi et al. (2025), studying 20 Indian teachers, documented fears that students might become overly dependent on AI and that critical thinking might suffer. Moorhouse (2024) noted concerns among Hong Kong teachers about reduced student independence. Song et al. (2025) found that Chinese teachers, as they progressed in AI integration, shifted focus from technical concerns to pedagogical impacts.

This cross-cultural consistency in cognitive risk focus suggests a shared professional identity concern: teachers across national contexts appear to conceptualize their role as cultivating independent thinking and worry that AI may undermine this core function.

8.4 Factors Promoting Adoption

International research identifies several consistent factors promoting AI adoption. Digital competence emerges as significant across studies. Galindo-Domínguez et al. (2024) found positive correlations between digital skills and AI attitudes among Spanish teachers. Musood and Kaur (2025) documented similar patterns among Indian pre-service teachers. Our German data, while not directly measuring digital competence, showed that lack of technical knowledge was cited by 19% as a barrier to use.

Familiarity and experience consistently predict more positive attitudes. Bateman (2024) found that US teachers more comfortable with ChatGPT perceived greater benefits and fewer risks. Our finding that 67% of German users reported positive attitude changes through experience aligns with this pattern. Moorhouse (2024) documented that Hong Kong teachers with prior ChatGPT experience showed greater readiness for professional use.

Leadership and organizational context also matter. Collie and Martin (2024) demonstrated that autonomy-supportive leadership predicted AI valuing among Australian teachers. While our study did not systematically examine leadership styles, the variation in usage rates across school types (94% in comprehensive schools versus 56% in primary schools for professional use) suggests organizational factors play a role.

8.5 Implications of the International Comparison

The consistency of findings across Germany, the United States, Australia, China, Hong Kong, and European contexts suggests that teacher AI adoption dynamics are shaped by factors that transcend national educational systems. The teacher-as-gatekeeper pattern, the focus on cognitive risks, and the positive effects of familiarity appear to be cross-cultural phenomena.

However, context-specific factors also matter. Our German data show variation across school types that may reflect specific organizational cultures and student populations. The high prohibition rates may also reflect particular German educational traditions emphasizing student independence and critical thinking.

These findings have implications for theory and policy. Theoretical models of teacher AI adoption must account for the gatekeeping dynamic and the professional identity concerns that underlie it. Policy interventions must address both universal patterns (such as the need for experience-based professional development) and context-specific factors (such as particular educational traditions and organizational cultures).

9 Discussion

9.1 Limitations of Established Technology Acceptance Models

The Technology Acceptance Model proves both partially useful and conceptually limited in analyzing generative AI adoption. Our empirical findings document that central TAM constructs do apply: 75% of respondents identified time savings as a clear benefit, and natural language interfaces substantially reduce technical barriers. Nevertheless, the model cannot fully explain the documented contrast between extensive private and more restrained educational use, particularly regarding student use. While our correlation analyses show that both private and educational use are associated with more positive attitudes—with educational use showing even stronger positive associations—this raises a different puzzle: if teachers who use AI in instruction hold more positive attitudes, why do they still restrict student access? This suggests that factors beyond individual attitudes, such as professional responsibility concerns and risk perceptions regarding students, shape adoption decisions.

Similarly, WSTM dimensions do not adequately explain why AI is or is not used for and in instruction. Teachers actually possess central competencies for effective complementary AI use. Successful AI interaction requires precise question formulation, adaptive conversation management based on response quality, metacognitive reflection on understanding gaps, and critical evaluation of outputs. All of these are core elements of pedagogical practice. Teachers daily orchestrate complex dialogue processes, adapt their communication to different learning prerequisites, and develop understanding through iterative deepening.

The low instructional AI use, particularly within lessons with students, despite these existing conversational and metacognitive competencies, thus points less to skill deficits than to a transfer problem. Teachers may not recognize that their pedagogical conversation competencies are transferable to AI interactions, or certain perceptual filters may prevent activation of these competencies. 60% explicitly express desire for AI support (Will), and tools are principally (though not universally) available. Nevertheless, 57% of teachers design their instruction without enabling students to collaborate with AI systems.

9.2 Network Complexities as a Structural Explanation

Regarding the break between private and professional use, network complexity theory offers a plausible explanation. Private AI use occurs in binary, self-controlled actor constellations, while educational application means embedding in multiple stakeholder networks. Data protection regulations block popular systems such as ChatGPT in many schools; existing assessment logics collide with AI support; and social control mechanisms through colleagues and school leadership communicate explicit or implicit expectations regarding appropriate pedagogical practice.

This network complexity could transform AI from a cooperative to a potentially resistant actor and can explain why the same individuals evaluate AI systems differently depending on context.

9.3 The Experience-Attitude Paradox in Educational AI Use

Correlation analyses reveal a striking pattern: teachers who use AI in instruction report *more* positive attitudes than those who do not, with stronger correlations than for private use alone. Educational users perceive AI as making their lives easier ($\rho=.49$), find it enjoyable ($\rho=.57$), trust AI suggestions more ($\rho=.44$), feel less overwhelmed ($\rho=-.32$), and report less fear ($\rho=-.21$). These associations are consistently stronger than for private use frequency.

This creates a theoretical puzzle. If educational AI use is associated with such positive attitudes, why do these same teachers restrict student access? The answer appears to lie in the differentiation between attitudes toward *own* use and attitudes toward *student* use. While teachers who use AI educationally also view student use more favorably (showing positive correlations with beliefs about independence, learning outcomes, and differentiation), they nonetheless maintain gatekeeping functions rooted in professional responsibility concerns.

Qualitative data illuminate this apparent paradox: teachers recognize AI’s benefits from personal experience while simultaneously perceiving cognitive risks for students. The 89% focus on cognitive threats in risk assessments suggests that positive personal experience does not eliminate concerns about student dependency, loss of critical thinking, or reduced independence. Teachers may reason: “AI helps me, but students lack the metacognitive skills to use it appropriately.”

This finding aligns with international research documenting that familiarity correlates with positive attitudes while also suggesting that experience-based attitude change operates differently for self-directed versus other-directed judgments.

9.4 Attitude Change Through Experience

Our findings strongly confirm that practical experience leads to more positive attitudes, with educational use showing even stronger positive associations than private use alone. 64% of German teachers report positive attitude changes through AI use, with only a small minority reporting worsening. International studies confirm this pattern: Bateman (2024) found familiarity correlated with positive attitudes among US teachers, and Moorhouse (2024) documented that prior experience predicted readiness among Hong Kong teachers.

This finding has important implications for professional development. Simply providing information about AI may be less effective than creating opportunities for guided, low-stakes experimentation. The transition from awareness to adoption appears to require practical experience that allows teachers to develop personal familiarity and recognize the applicability of existing competencies.

9.5 The Differentiation Exception

Notably, private usage frequency correlates significantly with only one dimension of student use assessment: the belief that AI facilitates differentiation and individual support ($\rho = .19, p < .05$). Differentiation thus appears to be a key factor where positive usage experiences directly translate into pedagogical expectations.

This finding may reflect the particular resonance between AI capabilities and a recognized challenge in teaching. Differentiated instruction is widely acknowledged as important but difficult to implement systematically given class sizes and time constraints. AI’s potential to provide individualized feedback, generate materials at different levels, and support students with diverse needs may represent a clear “use case” that connects personal experience with professional application.

9.6 Professional Identity and Transformation

Our findings, viewed alongside international research, suggest that teacher AI adoption is shaped not only by technology acceptance factors but by deeper professional identity concerns. The focus on cognitive risks, including loss of critical thinking, reduced independence, and diminished creativity, reflects anxieties about the changing nature of education.

A possible interpretation is that AI is perceived as a challenge to the established role of teachers as autonomous designers of teaching-learning processes, requiring a shift toward co-construction in socio-technical learning environments. The dominant loss anxieties (“creativity loss,” “loss of

critical thinking”) further suggest a substitutive rather than complementary mindset. AI is primarily perceived as replacement for human capabilities, not as their amplification.

This perspective suggests that professional development for AI integration must address not only technical skills and pedagogical applications but also teacher beliefs about the nature of their profession and the possibilities for human-AI collaboration. Deep changes often require disorienting experiences that challenge existing interpretive frameworks. AI systems that challenge familiar role conceptions and routines may create potential for transformative educational processes, provided these are pedagogically accompanied and addressed in professional reflection spaces.

10 Implications and Recommendations

Based on our findings and the international comparison, we offer three sets of recommendations:

10.1 Professional Development

Professional development should extend beyond technical qualification to address values, beliefs, and role conceptions. Specific recommendations include:

1. **Experience-based learning:** Create opportunities for low-stakes experimentation with AI tools, allowing teachers to develop familiarity and recognize the transferability of existing competencies.
2. **Reflective practice:** Include structured reflection on professional identity, examining beliefs about human versus machine capabilities and possibilities for complementary collaboration.
3. **Peer learning:** Facilitate collegial experimentation and exchange, as social learning contexts may help teachers navigate the transition from awareness to adoption.
4. **Focus on differentiation:** Given the consistent finding that differentiation represents a bridge between personal experience and pedagogical application, professional development might emphasize AI for individualized instruction.

10.2 School Development

School development requires legal certainty and supportive organizational contexts:

1. **Clear policies:** Develop explicit guidelines for AI use by teachers and students, addressing data protection, academic integrity, and appropriate applications.
2. **Supportive leadership:** Foster autonomy-supportive leadership styles that encourage experimentation while providing clear expectations.
3. **Infrastructure:** Ensure access to appropriate AI tools that comply with data protection requirements, removing technical barriers to adoption.
4. **Spaces for experimentation:** Create formal and informal opportunities for teachers to share experiences, discuss challenges, and develop collective approaches.

10.3 Education Policy

Education policy should acknowledge the cultural and professional dimensions of AI integration:

1. **Teacher preparation:** Integrate AI education into initial teacher preparation programs, ensuring that beginning teachers enter the profession with familiarity and experience.
2. **Research support:** Fund longitudinal research on AI integration, enabling evidence-based policy development.
3. **Stakeholder engagement:** Involve teachers in policy development, recognizing their expertise and addressing their concerns.
4. **Balanced communication:** Communicate both opportunities and risks of AI in education, avoiding both uncritical enthusiasm and excessive caution.

11 Conclusion

This study has documented a paradoxical pattern in teacher AI adoption: educators embrace AI for personal and professional purposes while restricting student access. Drawing on the LENS-AI study of 381 German teachers and situating findings within international research, we have shown that this pattern is not unique to Germany but represents a cross-cultural phenomenon.

The teacher-as-gatekeeper dynamic appears rooted in professional identity concerns, particularly worries about cognitive risks to students. Teachers across national contexts perceive themselves as protectors of student independence and critical thinking and view AI as potentially threatening these core educational goals. This finding challenges simple technology acceptance explanations and suggests that AI adoption in education is shaped by deeper cultural and professional factors.

At the same time, practical experience consistently promotes more positive attitudes. The 64% of German teachers reporting positive attitude changes through use, along with similar findings internationally, suggests that experience-based professional development may be more effective than information-only approaches.

The policy implications are clear: professional development must address values and role conceptions, not just technical skills; schools need supportive contexts with clear policies and leadership support; and education policy must take seriously the professional and cultural dimensions of AI integration.

Future research should examine longitudinal patterns of AI adoption, investigate the specific mechanisms through which experience shapes attitudes, and compare policy interventions across educational systems. The rapid evolution of AI technology ensures that these questions will remain relevant as educators continue to navigate the integration of increasingly capable AI systems into teaching and learning.

The data presented here represent a snapshot of a rapidly changing landscape. However, the underlying dynamics—including the tension between personal benefit and professional responsibility, the focus on cognitive risks, and the importance of experience—are likely to persist even as specific technologies evolve. Understanding these dynamics is essential for realizing the potential of AI to support, rather than undermine, educational goals.

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